

A Study on Adopting Shadowing Technique to Improve Pronunciation Competence of Juniors Majoring in English at Ho Chi Minh university of Food Industry.

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ABSTRACT

Because of the differences between English and Vietnamese pronunciation, occasionally it is hard for Vietnamese learners to pronounce English words correctly. Therefore, there have been a number of pronunciation learning methods introduced to English-majored students. Among them, shadowing technique has been likely to be used widely to develop pronunciation skill. This study aims to investigate the efficiency of applying shadowing technique to enhance Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry learners English pronunciation ability. The study was conducted within the period of 1 week of 10 juniors majoring in English at HUFU. The data were evaluated by Elsa app in a hope to show how those students good on pronunciation after a week applying the Shadowing method. The technique might open up a new studying strategy in learning English pronunciation.

Keywords: shadowing technique, English-majored students, pronunciation skill, awareness .

1. Introduction

According to (Stern, 1983), language problems can result from the psychological, sociological, or linguistic perspective. By focusing on the acquisition of pronunciation, a learner's mother tongue or first language (L1) is one of the most obstacles. In fact, instead of saying /aɪ wɒnt / many Vietnamese learning English as a Foreign Language tend to say /aɪ wɒn /. This means that Vietnamese phonetic features generate not only the limitation of Vietnamese word-final sounds but also other pronunciation mistakes. Nowadays, English is an essential demand for schooling and job opportunities. According to “English as an official language in Vietnam: would it work?” (Sen, 2015) states that by having English skills, applicants are likely to be more marketable. This is because of the ability to catch up with world news, which translates into knowledge and power. Although it takes most of the Vietnamese students studying English in secondary and high school, many learners are not competent enough to communicate fluently. This phenomenon might come from too much grammar focusing on school education. According to “English teaching in Vietnam: Teacher ‘re-education’” (Toan, 2015) indicates that Vietnamese schools have been focusing on English grammar and reading comprehension for years, as a result, not only students but also their teachers are trained to be experts in grammatical structures and vocabulary, but not to use these skills as a language. Therefore, it is not surprising for non- native speakers to make mistakes with pronunciation but after learning English for a long time with the lack of

pronunciation ability is an unexpected result. This reality might make a lot of students feel doubt about their ability in speaking English. This means that English learners avoid speaking because they do not want to let anyone know that their English is bad, and their English teachers cannot correct their mistakes in pronunciation. Therefore, the shadowing method is the best way for these students. This method would assist learners in phonological awareness and enhance the pronunciation by copying not all vocabulary, structures that native speakers use, pronunciation, and intonation native speakers say. The most interesting part of this method is that students can practice on their own by recording what they have already said and comparing it to the original source.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Definition

According to (Hamanda, 2015) Shadowing method refers to shadowing reading and listening, which means that language learners “speak along” in time with an audio text sharing the common features with karaoke. Similarly, (Hamanda, 2015) illustrated that shadowing is originally used for training novice interpreters. However, she affirmed that this technique is more necessary for EFL students to enhance their listening and speaking ability. Besides, (Tamai, 1997), the pioneer of shadowing research in Japan’s English as a foreign language (EFL) context, re-defined Lambert’s definition of shadowing as “an act or a task of listening in which the learner tracks the heard speech and repeats it as accurately as possible whereas listening attentively to the incoming information”. (Celce-Murcia, 1996) further points out that shadowing, along with repetition, mirroring, and imitative conversation techniques (Goodwin, 2004) is taken into account one of the oral teaching methods used for imitating native speakers’ intonation patterns at the discourse level.

2.2. The Gap

According to (Wei, 2006), pronunciation should emphasize on intonation, stress (word and sentence level stress), and rhythm. However, Lin, Fan, and Chen (Lin, 2011) disagree with Wei’s point of view by suggest that, English learners might pay more attention to the sounds (word pronunciation), vocabulary, and grammar when they are listening to English rather than intonation and rhythm. Therefore, this statement additionally points out that this is often the explanation why several English learners complain about the speed of the listening texts being too quick from time to time.

(Moussa-Inaty, 2012) found that simultaneous reading and listening was significantly less effective than reading solely in learning new vocabulary and translating sentences among 38 university students in the EFL context. This statement might be unexpected for learners.. At any levels of learners, without knowing the first thing of vocabulary, it is impossible to speak in English, let alone improve pronunciation. Therefore, the effectiveness of the Shadowing method

could encounter several doubts of learners.

In terms of the shadowing skill of reproduction accuracy, according to (Shiki, 2010) reports that the reproduction rate likely hits the ceiling point after four to five shadowing trials. Although this finding was based on a one-day session involving 48 Japanese university students, and the implication may be limited to the conditions of their study, this ceiling phenomenon was observed in (Tamai K. , 2002) studies as well. However, the shadowing materials were set at the average of the participants in proficiency levels in these studies, and different materials with the same difficulty level and speed were used throughout the study period. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that those at lower proficiency levels show more improvement than those at a higher proficiency level, as they are assumed to have more room for improvement. For learners in lower proficiency level who is claimed to be faster than the others may still have to be compelled to take a great deal of time to accomplish the first stage in practicing Shadowing method which is mentioned by (McLaughlin, 1978). McLaughlin (McLaughlin, 1978) who considers second language learning as two performance behaviors based on theoretical basis for the 'shadowing' technique. He indicates the processes as follows: in initially the speakers perform slowly and hesitantly, then sometimes having a great deal of conscious awareness and finally in the course of time, the whole process can be done automatically without reflection.

From the (O'Malley, 1989) point of view, the listening comprehension process that L2 learners typically take in includes: bottom-up processing and top-down processing. The former is the processing that starts from a minimum element of speech, for instance: sound forming a morpheme, a word, a sentence and the context and appropriate use of the language, which leads to comprehension. On the contrary, top-down processing is a process that starts from the context and only recognized words to guess the meaning by compensating for missed words. This bottom-up process is applied effectively in Shadowing according to (Kadota, 2007) (Kadota, Shadowing, Ondoku to Eigo Shutoku no Kagaku [The science of shadowing, oral reading], 2012). By forcing active subvocalization in Word Memory, author (Kadota, Shadowing, Ondoku to Eigo Shutoku no Kagaku [The science of shadowing, oral reading], 2012) states that this method would alter the brain to utilize its restricted resources for higher-level linguistic process, similar to native and advanced L2 speakers. In addition, (Derwing, 1997) also states that the use of intonation at the discourse level, both intelligibility increased and learner' fossilized pronunciation are also found to be improved.

3. The Study

Participants: Totally there were 10 English major students whose language proficiency ranged from A2 to B1 on Common European Framework for Reference willingly participate in this research which lasted 1 week in a hope of improving their pronunciation through applying Shadowing method. All the participants were juniors at HUFU. They are required to commit to practice this method 1 hour per day involving 30' after waking up and 30' before going to bed.

Material: By using 10 videos which are under 6 minutes from Ted channel, every student was given different video. Moreover, students have to guarantee that recordings was sent at the end of the day (before 12p.m)

Diagnostic assessment: At the beginning, by using Elsa app, a 12-sentence test¹ was conducted by Elsa app to assess these major students with pronunciation. (Becker, 2019)ELSA is an AI-powered app for the language learners in the world to learn to speak English more fluently. With speech technology and AI, this app can detect people's pronunciation mistakes with 95%+ accuracy. ELSA Speak listens to the way language learners pronounce words, sentences or conversations. Then Elsa will pinpoint exact errors and provide real-time feedback on pronunciation including on individual sounds, rhythm and intonations. For the first time signing up, there is a test to evaluate students' ability with five criteria of pronunciation, fluency, intonation, stress and listening. ELSA also has a free version for Android and IOS allowed users to 7 day trial. After the morning of seventh day, all students did a test on it again to get results.

4. Finding And Dicussion

With investigating the impact of combing Shadowing technique, two tests were delivered in the beginning and at the end of the course with the results below.

Figure 1.The deviation of learner's performance after 1 week applying method
The pie chart illustrates a positive impact on those junior willingly attending this study's performance after adopting Shadowing method. As we can be seen from the

chart, it is noticeable that the majority of students had better academic results at 60%. However, there was a similar pattern of the proportion of students between whose pronunciation competence decreased and kept stable, reaching at 20%. In brief, the Shadowing technique gives causes for hope and confidence in improve pronunciation of learners.

Figure 2: The students' results based on Elsa app

The bar chart above illustrates data about the results of pre-test and post-test of 10 students whose levels ranged from A2 to B1. Overall, a total of 6 students had higher scores in the post-test, which means that most students showed higher performance after a week.

It is noticeable that the deviation between 2 tests of students level B1 was trivial, maximum at 15 %, and minimum at 10%, compared to level A2 students, maximum at 25% and minimum at 8%. Therefore the data suggested that the Shadowing technique had a significant influence on learners' pronunciation, especially low levels students.

Figure 3: The percentage of improvement on phonological awareness

The study shows that many positive effects on learners' phonological awareness. First of all, the highest percentage of improvement belonged to stress was at 65% while the proportion of silent sound experienced at the lowest point of 45%. *Stress was considered as the least difficult element in pronunciation because it was only necessary for learners to memorize the rules of stress in different syllables and they were able to pronounce correctly. Before the study, stress is the element that is expected to be the hardest part for learners to improve.* According to Le Thuy Chi (Le, 2006) In Vietnamese, it is said that all words can be said to be the mono-syllabic words including some exceptions of compound words, which also have separate syllable and distinctive tone. For example: long lanh, rung rinh, dat dao... Because of the difference between Vietnamese and English, Vietnamese learners might struggle when they learn how to pronounce poly-syllabic words with stress patterns in English. At the beginning, Vietnamese students, are likely to pronounce all the syllables with the same loudness, length and pitch. Therefore, this feature is considered as a negative influence of our mother tongue. Therefore, it seems that the students' native language can be counted for the reasons why stress errors occur.

Furthermore, intonation stood in second place with 60% of the class in improvement. *Learners imitated the way native speakers performed speaking in videos and tried to read out repeatedly with a similar intonation and they were allowed to practice various contextual shadowing of one sentence. As a result, they could realize the keywords which played the most significant role in the whole utterance.*

Besides, the percentage of consonants reached the 59% mark, with the proportion for vowels not far behind (55%). This result might come from the similarity between English and Vietnamese. According to (Nguyen, 2009) *English consonants shared some similarities in oral shape and phonological constitution with mother tongue of Vietnamese such as t,b,m,n,.....* Therefore, realizing and finding out the correct pronunciation of English consonants can be easier. In contrast, students faced several difficulties in pronouncing ending sounds. *This might come from the impact of the mother tongue. In other words, pronouncing English final consonants and consonant*

clusters properly is one of the most difficult parts that Vietnamese learners have to encounter from the very beginning because there are a number of consonants that do not exist in Vietnam and vice versa (Nguyen T. T., 2007)

In contrast, although the study indicated several benefits of applying the Shadowing method, there might be some drawbacks. At TED, every speaker presents information in a way that is both compelling and 100% credible and, the content should be based on information that has survived scrutiny by experts in the field. (TED Ideas worth spreading). Therefore, the first reason is about the material, 10 videos from the TED channel might be so formal and academic while in reality, learners may not have a chance to use this vocabulary on a regular basis. The second reason results from the size of the participants. 10 participants might be quite small, which to some extent affected the outcomes of the study and generalization of the whole study to cover other groups of participants which had various features. The final reason is about the time which was limited in 1 week. As a result, it is possible that there might be some deficiencies in the results of every learner because the learning ability of individuals is totally different. Precisely, a student whose initial result has no differences, which does not mean that after the result of 1 month or 2 weeks would be the same. Finally, the study had to confront some limitations; however, the benefits that this study brought about a positive improvement of learners' pronunciation can be undeniable.

5. Conclusion

The study has shown a number of significant impacts of the Shadowing technique on pronunciation improvement. First, the whole participants addressed highly progressive in pronunciation performance. This means that being able to cope with this new method, learners can gain knowledge about most of the aspects of pronunciation; however, the study still experienced some drawbacks: time, size, and common words. Second, it is notable that some modifications in phonological expression fixed during the implementations, which can result in not only better pronunciation skill but also speaking skill in the long-term. It is recommended that more studies should be conducted to investigate how the development of information technology and other attributes such as how AI can intervene with learners' motivation in learning English.

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APPENDIX

(1) The pre-test and post-test:

Listen and repeat 12 English sentences below:

1. People are talking about what comes next after the pandemic, and they're calling it the new normal.
2. As we shift back to our normal lives in the coming years, we'll have to do many things in new ways.
3. Various parts of our lives will undergo long-term changes, including employment, education, technology, and even social behavior and relationships.
4. Some changes will be guided by government measures, while others will be based on personal decisions and choices.
5. People in many industries are adjusting to remote work. Video calls and online collaboration tools are more important than ever.
6. Similarly, online learning is becoming an essential part of education, from childhood education to college and graduate school.
7. Along with adopting new ways to work and study, we should think about how to enjoy our leisure time and maintain meaningful relationships.
8. Video calls are a good way to keep in touch, and they've become very common as a way to socialize too.
9. These calls can include anything from casual hangouts and birthday parties to more formal events, like family reunions and weddings.
10. While the economy isn't fully open yet in many places, people are returning to some of their usual activities and appointments.
11. Nobody knows what the future could hold or how we'll tackle the challenges that are bound to come up in the next few years.
12. I feel confident, however, that we will join together and find the ways to make the most of this new normal.